

SAGES CVS Challenge - Towards robust & available Surgical AI: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

SAGES CVS Challenge - Towards robust & available Surgical AI

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CVS Lighthouse Challenge

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

With the increasing permeation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in all facets of medicine, the expectations of the technology's potential escalates. Widespread research applications of Computer Vision (CV) and Machine Learning (ML) to minimally invasive surgery promise to enhance clinical perception, support time and safety-critical decision-making, as well as other applications for AI in education and certification -- ultimately increasing surgical safety. Before these approaches can be translated into clinical practice there is an undeniable need for widespread validation and evaluation of model robustness across distributions related to patient and data diversity. Moreover, in the face of time-critical decisions impacting patient lives, the algorithms' efficiency, correctness, and handling of uncertainty, pertaining to model limitations and subjectivity of ground truth labels, have to be quantified.

Due to its highly standardized approach, and globally large case volume, laparoscopic cholecystectomy – the minimally invasive removal of the gallbladder - has become a benchmark procedure for computational exploration of surgical video data. During laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the Critical View of Safety (CVS) offers a well-defined, clinically validated, and universally recognized surgical safety step to ensure the correct identification of relevant anatomy. Failure to achieve the CVS can result in undesired injury critical structures, such as common bile duct injuries, leading to detrimental consequences for patient outcomes and survival. Despite widespread research endeavors offering promising results for computational CVS assessment, there is no translation into clinical practice. The Society of American Gastrointestinal and Endoscopic Surgeons Critical View of Safety Challenge (SAGES CVS Challenge), currently held at MICCAI 2024, targets algorithmic accuracy, robustness, and certainty in CVS assessment during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The SAGES CVS Challenge offers an unprecedented infrastructure, characterized by multidisciplinary expertise from surgeons, computer scientists, and industry, meticulous data collection and curation resulting in a large and diverse global dataset,

and expert consensus-based ground truth labels generated through a quality controlled annotation framework. The extensive CVS Challenge dataset, comprising contributions from 67 surgeons from 57 countries, and all 6 continents, reflects a vast variety of patient, surgeon, and case characteristics required to ensure the real-world applicability of surgical AI. For more details regarding the 2024 SAGES CVS Challenge, we refer to the published challenge proposal and website (www.cvschallenge.org).

Simultaneously to achieving algorithmic accuracy in CVS classification, the increasingly high computational barrier to enable widespread deployment of AI systems for surgical safety has to be overcome. Thus the 2025 SAGES CVS Lighthouse Challenge (CVS Lighthouse) will revisit the CVS classification task, while expanding the scope of the challenge to target two additional goals: (1) computational efficiency and (2) explicit surgical scene understanding. The former is particularly relevant for applicability in low-resource settings, while the latter is crucial in developing trustworthy AI systems. To measure progress towards these goals, we introduce two new sub-challenges: a CPU-only evaluation sub-challenge and a scene segmentation sub-challenge.

The SAGES CVS Lighthouse Challenge, targeting accurate, robust and uncertainty aware CVS classification, expands beyond the first iteration of the challenge to encompass computational efficiency and surgical scene understanding. The challenge has the potential to translate impactful AI applications into widely accessible data-driven insights for enhanced surgical safety. Deploying accurate, reliable, generalizable and trustworthy AI in resource mindful way will enable globally dispersed surgeons to use resulting CVS classification technology and democratize access to technology-empowered surgical safety.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Surgical Safety, AI Efficiency, Uncertainty Quantification, Surgical AI, Minimally Invasive Surgery, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

There are countless research applications centered around the detection and prediction of the CVS, many of them centered around the publicly available datasets Cholec80 and CholecSeg8k. Yet clinical translation and deployment in the operating room remains elusive. This is largely due to the limited generalizability of AI architectures developed almost entirely on localized, homogenous datasets. Moreover, the extensive computational requirements to run established CVS classification models is widely available in large academic centers and research institutions but prohibit the deployment in less resource-strong settings, which includes most operating rooms.

The Lighthouse CVS Lighthouse Challenge ("SAGES CVS - towards robustness and available Surgical AI") addresses this critical gap by leveraging an unprecedentedly diverse dataset and adding 2 crucial sub-goals: (1) evaluating computational efficiency, and (2) evaluating holistic 2D scene understanding, goals which can expand the reach of automated CVS assessment and contribute to increased trust in such systems.

The challenge is organized by the Society of American Gastrointestinal and Endoscopic Surgeons (SAGES), which is an umbrella organization for a large number of US and International Hospitals. Beyond this large community surgeons from over 60 institutions have contributed to the dataset and are actively following the challenge's progress. This unprecedented challenge has required the collaboration and coordination of numerous clinical and technical leaders from academia and industry, as well as a large body of highly skilled medical experts to curate what will be one of the most diverse datasets in surgical data science. Moreover, the challenge required the development of sophisticated infrastructure to solve unique issues that appear at this scale of data collection, annotation, and interdisciplinary coordination, which we believe will serve as a reference for future challenges in the space.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Within the CVS Challenge we conduct three (3) subchallenges. Each of these subchallenges will target different aspects of CVS evaluation.

A) CVS Criteria Classification

First, we assess overall model performance with respect to (1) classification accuracy, (2) uncertainty-awareness compared to medical experts' confidence assessment and (3) robustness to demonstrate safe and reliable CVS classification across a wide variety of clinical and demographic scenarios.

B) Resource-Constrained CVS Criteria Classification

Secondly, we evaluate the three tiers of CVS Criteria Classification (accuracy / uncertainty awareness / robustness) under computational budget constraints (4 CPUs, 16 GB CPU RAM) to investigate deployment in low resource settings, assessing democratization of the technology.

C) Instance Segmentation of Hepatocystic Anatomy

Finally, we evaluate instance segmentation of the six predominantly clinically relevant classes of hepatocystic anatomy to assess interpretability of algorithmic CVS assessment, aiming to promote trust in the resulting AI systems.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Full day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

50

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Within a year after MICCAI 2025, the SAGES CVS Challenge organizers will assemble a joint publication, summarizing the challenge results and disclosing the top three winning methods (1st, 2nd, 3rd).

- To be recognized for their submission all members of each challenge team must individually acknowledge the SAGES CVS Challenge Participation Agreement.

As the SAGES CVS Lighthouse Challenge is based on the established pipeline for data acquisition and annotation, the various contributors will be recognized in the publication.

- Annotators will be recognized as full coauthors in the final manuscript, after the successful completion of the SAGES CVS Challenge Annotation School (70% interrater agreement with predefined expert ground truth) and all videos assigned to them by the challenge organizers (minimum 250 videos) will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript. Annotators contributing less than the assigned 250 videos will be recognized in consortium authorship.

- Data Donors, are required to contribute a minimum of 50 unique laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos, and metadata through the designated Video Acquisition Portal will be acknowledged in a `Data Donor Consortium`.

- Advisory Committee members, who actively contributed to the composition of the CVS Challenge Annotation Protocol and Framework, the Annotation Process or Evaluation Pipeline will be acknowledged in an `Advisory Committee Consortium`.

Besides the listed authorship criteria specific to the co-authors role and contribution, all co-authors and consortium members are required to

- actively contribute to the composition and revision of the manuscript by critically assessing important intellectual content.

- give final approval of the manuscript version before publication.

- attend and actively participate in at least one official SAGES CVS Challenge summit is required to be eligible for co-authorship or consortium co-authorship.

The challenge organizers will determine the final order of authorship. After the final publication of the challenge manuscript, the participating teams are welcome to publish their individual results under citation of the official challenge manuscripts and all previous manuscripts summarizing the CVS Challenge.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

4000 gpu hours for compute per participant

TASK 1: SAGES CVS - Towards robust & available Surgical AI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

With the increasing permeation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in all facets of medicine, the expectations of the technology's potential escalates. Widespread research applications of Computer Vision (CV) and Machine Learning (ML) to minimally invasive surgery promise to enhance clinical perception, support time and safety-critical decision-making, as well as other applications for AI in education and certification -- ultimately increasing surgical safety. Before these approaches can be translated into clinical practice there is an undeniable need for widespread validation and evaluation of model robustness across distributions related to patient and data diversity. Moreover, in the face of time-critical decisions impacting patient lives, the algorithms' efficiency, correctness, and handling of uncertainty, pertaining to model limitations and subjectivity of ground truth labels, have to be quantified.

Due to its highly standardized approach, and globally large case volume, laparoscopic cholecystectomy – the minimally invasive removal of the gallbladder - has become a benchmark procedure for computational exploration of surgical video data. During laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the Critical View of Safety (CVS) offers a well-defined, clinically validated, and universally recognized surgical safety step to ensure the correct identification of relevant anatomy. Failure to achieve the CVS can result in undesired injury critical structures, such as common bile duct injuries, leading to detrimental consequences for patient outcomes and survival. Despite widespread research endeavors offering promising results for computational CVS assessment, there is no translation into clinical practice. The Society of American Gastrointestinal and Endoscopic Surgeons Critical View of Safety Challenge (SAGES CVS Challenge), currently held at MICCAI 2024, targets algorithmic accuracy, robustness, and certainty in CVS assessment during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The SAGES CVS Challenge offers an unprecedented infrastructure, characterized by multidisciplinary expertise from surgeons, computer scientists, and industry, meticulous data collection and curation resulting in a large and diverse global dataset, and expert consensus-based ground truth labels generated through a quality controlled annotation framework. The extensive CVS Challenge dataset, comprising contributions from 67 surgeons from 57 countries, and all 6 continents, reflects a vast variety of patient, surgeon, and case characteristics required to ensure the real-world applicability of surgical AI. For more details regarding the 2024 SAGES CVS Challenge, we refer to the published challenge proposal and website (www.cvschallenge.org).

In the 2025 SAGES CVS Lighthouse Challenge, we are expanding the scope of the challenge to target two additional goals: (1) computational efficiency and (2) explicit surgical scene understanding. The former is particularly relevant for applicability in low-resource settings, while the latter is crucial in developing trustworthy AI systems. To measure progress towards these goals, we introduce two new sub-challenges: a CPU-only evaluation sub-challenge and a scene segmentation sub-challenge.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Surgical Safety, AI Efficiency, Uncertainty Quantification, Surgical AI, Minimally Invasive Surgery, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Ozanan Meireles, MD (1,7), Nicolas Padoy, PhD (2), Daniel Hashimoto, MD (3), Jennifer Eckhoff, MD (1,4), Deepak Alapatt, MSc (2), Guy Rosman, PHD (1), Pietro Mascagni, MD, PhD (2), Jean-Paul Mazallier, PhD (2), Xiang Li, PhD (5), Zhiliang Lyu, MSc (5), Sarah Choksi, MD (6), Filippo Filicori, MD (6), Yutong Ban, PhD (1), Aditya Murali, MSc (2), Andrea Naclerio, MSc (2), Lorenzo Arboit, MD (2)

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b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

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Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention 2025 in South Korea (MICCAI)

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://www.cvschallenge.org/>

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.cvschallenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top three performing (first, second, third place) teams will receive awards. The awards stipend is to be determined.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods (first, second, and third place) will be included in the final publication and publicly displayed on the challenge website (www.cvschallenge.org). The team members will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript, providing a SAGES CVS Challenge participation agreement was signed.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Within a year after MICCAI 2025, the SAGES CVS Challenge organizers will assemble a joint publication, summarizing the challenge results and disclosing the top three winning methods (1st, 2nd, 3rd).

- To be recognized for their submission all members of each challenge team must individually acknowledge the SAGES CVS Challenge Participation Agreement.

The challenge organizers will determine the final order of authorship. After the final publication of the challenge manuscript, the participating teams are welcome to publish their individual results under citation of the official challenge manuscripts and all previous manuscripts summarizing the CVS Challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The submission instructions will be published on the CVS Challenge website. Participants are required to submit their results via a docker container. The model output format will be published along with the instructions and sample code. There can be one submission per team with three separate docker containers, each addressing one of the three sub-challenges.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The organizing team will have a 2-week validation period during which participants can submit their docker containers and check (1) whether their container produces valid output, and (2) the official challenge metrics evaluated on a defined subset of training videos.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

03/28: Registration Opens!

05/09: Release of Segmentation Annotations, Sub-Challenge C Guidelines

06/27: Release of Official Submission Instructions

07/18: Registration Deadline

07/28 - 08/15: Submission Validation Period

08/29: Challenge Submission Deadline

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Data donation was performed with the approval of regional Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) at each donor's institution, as agreed upon in the platform's terms and conditions. All data is de-identified through the SAGES Video Acquisition Portal, created by Surgical Safety Technologies. Consequently, no additional IRB approval is required for the CVS Challenge.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Participants will be provided with an example notebook and evaluation script in July 2025.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are required to submit their inference algorithms and associated model weights into a docker container. The challenge organizers will ensure that the participants' source code and model weights remain confidential and will not be disclosed publicly during the evaluation phase. After the challenge is finished, code and model weights from voluntary participating teams with leading scores will be made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The CVS Lighthouse Challenge is organized by the Society of American Gastrointestinal and Endoscopic Surgeons (SAGES) with financial backing from the SAGES Foundation, Intuitive Surgical, Olympus, Medtronic Inc., and Surgical Safety Technologies. During the challenge, the industrial sponsors will not have access to the test data. However, they may access the data once the complete dataset is publicly released after the challenge concludes.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,Assistance,Treatment planning,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation

- Tracking

Classification, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Both the challenge and target cohorts consist of patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, a common minimally invasive procedure to remove the gallbladder due to inflammation or other pathologies. The Critical View of Safety (CVS), established by Strasberg et al. in the Journal of the American College of Surgeons in 2010, is a clinically validated safety measure during laparoscopic cholecystectomy aimed at preventing common bile duct injuries, a serious complication seriously affecting patient morbidity and mortality. The CVS involves dissecting and isolating three anatomical landmarks, which are visually distinguishable in the intraabdominal video obtained from the laparoscope. The video data is collected using various laparoscopes from different manufacturers, enhancing data diversity and ensuring a representative sample of the real-world population. The CVS Challenge focuses on classifying these criteria.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Same as target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Intra abdominal endoscopic video data.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Challenge participants will receive 90-second segments of laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos, with the endpoint determined as the time of clipping of one of the critical anatomic structures composing the CVS (cystic duct or cystic artery). Alongside the video, the ground truth annotations will be provided:

- Per Video (Were the 3 CVS criteria achieved in the overall video? Yes / No) = 3 Binary Labels x 3 annotators
- Per Frame (Were the 3 CVS criteria achieved in this frame? Yes / No) = 3 Binary Labels x 18 Frames x 3 annotators
- Annotation Confidence (How sure was the annotation of the 3 CVS criteria for this case? 0-1 / not confident-confident) = 1 probabilistic label x 3 annotators
- Segmentation Per Frame (Hepatocystic Anatomy Segmentation of 7 classes) = 1 Segmentation Mask x 1 Frame
- 1 Segmentation Mask x 3 Frames in 300 Test Videos

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Besides the procedure type (laparoscopic cholecystectomy) participants will only receive pseudonymized categories about all demographic and clinical information (i.e. metadata) associated with the video is provided at the discretion of the individual data donors in compliance with regionally obtained institutional approval. This information is only provided to participants in anonymized form with the original information solely accessible by challenge organizers for the purpose of data splits. Patients' sex or gender is not acquired and is irrelevant to the proposed question. This demographic and clinical information includes:

- Country of Data Origin (anonymized)
- Laparoscope Type (category) i.e. manufacturer
- Robotic Surgery (binary label) i.e. as opposed to conventional laparoscopy
- Additional Imaging modalities used i.e. Indocyanine Green (ICG) Use (binary label)
- Additional intraoperative diagnostics i.e. Intraoperative Cholangiography (IOC) (binary label)

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data consists of endoscopic video obtained from inside of the patient's abdomen during minimally invasive cholecystectomy.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm targets classification probabilities of the three criteria composing the CVS. These criteria, defined in the consensus-based Annotation Protocol, are C1) 'two and only two tubular structures are seen connected to the gallbladder' referring to the Cystic Duct and Cystic Artery, C2) 'The hepatocystic triangle is cleared from fat and/or connective tissue so that unimpeded view is obtained' and C3) 'The lower part of the gallbladder is dissected off the liver bed to expose the lower 1/3 of the cystic plate'.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Robustness, Hardware requirements

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The recording device manufacturer (laparoscope / robotic system manufacturer) is submitted alongside the video data at the discretion of the data donor and will serve to determine data splits. To participants, this information will be only provided in anonymized form (i.e. categories). Major manufacturers (Stryker, Storz, Olympus, Medtronic, Intuitive, Conmed) are well represented in this dataset (> 50 cases each).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The raw video data has been extensively preprocessed and standardized with respect to image encoding (h.264) and format (mp4). The data was annotated by a team of experienced surgical data scientists using a four-eye principle. Preannotation criteria included accurate deidentification (i.e., no out-of-body images in selected segment), no aborted procedure/alternative operative approaches (i.e., Fundus first approach), robotic vs. laparoscopic, ICG use yes or no, and IOC yes or no.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data was collected through data contributions from 67 surgeons in 57 countries and 6 continents and encompasses a wide diversity of patient demographics and procedural quality to reflect the worldwide diversity in patients and surgeons. Due to regionally variable data regulations and privacy concerns, specific locations of the source data (i.e. institution) cannot be disclosed. However, approximately 30% of the collected data (~300 videos) originates from low- and middle-income countries, according to the latest OECD listing.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

This diverse, global dataset of laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos spans various clinical characteristics, pertaining to operative modality (robotic/laparoscopic), different imaging modalities (white light / ICG), and intraoperative diagnostic measures (cholangiogram). The distribution of positive to negative examples of the CVS achieved / not achieved is reflective of the real-world population as experienced in the operating room.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each video in the dataset represents an individual patient's case and includes a 90-second segment. This segment begins 90 seconds before one of the relevant anatomic structures forming the CVS (cystic duct or artery) is clipped, corresponding to the time when the operating surgeon made an executive decision ("point of no return"). Besides the overall video classification of the three CVS criteria, individual frames, extracted at five-second intervals were annotated, resulting in 18 frames per video, to provide supplementary training data. Finally, we annotate 1 frame per training video, and 3 frames per testing video with segmentation masks. The training frames are sampled in a stratified fashion at either the 15s, 45s, or 75s mark in the video, while frames from each of these time-points are sampled from the testing videos.

We also measure the annotator's confidence in annotating a specific case (i.e. video) with CVS achievement on a 0-1 scale (0=not at all confident, 1=extremely confident), using this rating to derive the uncertainty-aware CVS reference labels.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The number of videos used for training vs testing will follow a traditional ~70-30 split. Therefore 700 videos will be released to participants and 300 videos will be retained to be used for evaluation purposes.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The traditional 70-30 split applied serves participants with an adequately sized training set to explore the vast variety of clinical and data attributes reflected and develop clinically meaningful, widely generalizable architectures. Moreover, it allows the challenge organizers to maintain a sufficient test set allowing for subsampling to test different aspects of robustness to distribution shifts.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The challenge organizers will ensure that the training and test sets are balanced with respect to the diverse variety of demographics and characteristics present in the dataset, such as devices and imaging modalities.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Each video (case) is annotated by three different annotators. The entire annotator pool entails over 40 onboarded annotators from different demographics.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Before annotation of the CVS, the dataset was pre-annotated by the organizing team (four-eye principle) to (1) exclude videos that did not meet the inclusion criteria (e.g., alternative operative approaches like Fundus-first

cholecystectomy, incomplete or aborted procedures, conversions to open surgery, out-of-body images in the 90-second segment of interest, and clipping of either the cystic duct or artery); and (2) Index the data based on clinical characteristics (e.g., robotic vs. laparoscopic procedures, use of fluorescent imaging/Indocyanine Green, and performance of an intraoperative cholangiogram). These clinical characteristics are used to create data splits for the subchallenges described later.

The CVS annotation protocol was refined from the guidelines found in <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.10916> through a three-round modified Delphi consensus involving clinical and technical Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) from the SAGES community, experts in safe cholecystectomy guidelines, and members of the CVS Advisory Committee. Any disagreements during the Delphi process were resolved through structured interviews with the KOLs. To enhance understanding, the protocol was supplemented with flashcards illustrating clinical examples and instructional videos. Based on the finalized protocol, the KOLs and Delphi participants annotated 60 videos each, with the resulting interrater agreement serving as the reference annotation for the `CVS Annotation School Dataset.` Annotators had to qualify for the SAGES CVS Challenge Annotation Team by completing a structured curriculum based on the protocol and CVS Annotation School Dataset. The curriculum entailed a 45-minute virtual onboarding session with a clinical member of the CVS challenge organizing team, to explain the objective of the challenge and details of the annotation protocol. Following the onboarding session, annotators were required to annotate the 60 videos in the `CVS Annotation School dataset` in a proficiency-based progression, achieving at least 70% interrater agreement with the predefined reference annotation.

The SAGES CVS Annotation Training followed these steps:

Annotation Protocol Composition in modified Delphi among clinical experts

Annotation School dataset annotation by clinical experts

Definition of reference annotation through interrater agreement among clinical experts annotators

Onboarding Call for recruited annotators

Annotation of Annotation School dataset

Interrater agreement of 70% with AC

Throughout the annotation process, videos were assigned randomly to annotators in equally sized batches in regular intervals (20 videos each two weeks). Annotators were closely monitored (timely completion of the assigned dataset), and the organizing team offered routine check-ins to maintain communication with the annotators.

The Segmentation annotation protocol was similarly developed following <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.10916>. To increase throughput, we outsourced frames to SuperAnnotate, a company specializing in annotation services for Computer Vision applications. We reviewed the initial masks annotated by SuperAnnotate in 3 separate rounds, with SuperAnnotate revising errors after each round. To ensure high-quality segmentation masks, the annotation review was carried out by a team of 4 surgical domain experts, who we trained according to <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.10916>. In the first round of annotation review, each expert reviewed 400 images (for a total of 1600 images segmented). Then, in the second round of annotation review, each expert reviewed a different set of 400 images, to ensure that each image was reviewed by two separate experts, thereby limiting annotator bias. In the final round of review, frames with >3 revisions over the course of the annotation process were flagged and further checked by 2 additional expert annotators.

Each of the 6 annotated classes (Cystic Plate, Hepatocystic Triangle Dissection, Cystic Artery, Cystic Duct, Gallbladder, and Tool) were annotated on a per-instance basis. This is because they can either appear as multiple disjoint instance by definition (e.g. multiple surgical tools, multiple windows of the hepatocystic triangle dissection, two or more cystic arteries) or because they are divided into disjoint sub-parts in a particular frame (e.g. tool separating two parts of the gallbladder).

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Besides surgical trainees (residents and fellows) we onboarded medical students in their final year and surgical attendings. Video batches for annotation were assigned to annotators randomly. Annotators were recruited through an open call, and trained using the described annotation curriculum. Their annotation performance was monitored closely, and participation in regularly scheduled calls and timely completion of the assigned video batches was required to remain an active member of the SAGES CVS Annotation Team.

For the instance segmentation annotations, SuperAnnotate was first given a detailed annotation protocol with instructions on how to annotate each structure as well as various example cases and edge cases. They began by annotating an initial set of 30 images; following this initial annotation period, the initial annotation protocol was supplemented with an instruction document with examples of their common errors (e.g. missing cystic plate, oversegmentation of cystic duct) and the proper annotation protocol for these cases. Afterwards, they proceeded to annotate the 1600 frames of the Sages CVS Challenge Segmentation Dataset.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotations from each of the annotators are provided (without any merging) to the participants to use as they see fit during training. During inference, we use majority-vote for the 3 computational-efficiency sub-challenges and use individual annotator annotations to estimate model calibration in the computational-efficiency subchallenge.

In the case of segmentation, errors identified during annotation review are corrected. However, given the multi-round, multi-annotator annotation review process, there is the potential for conflicting annotation review feedback. We flag such instances as "difficult frames" that are mediated in a 3rd final round of annotation review by 2 separate expert annotators.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All raw videos have gone through pre-processing to standardize the image encoding (h.264) and format (mp4) and a preannotation pipeline to screen for the described exclusion criteria and annotate clinical characteristics. No other specific preprocessing will be performed before providing data to the participants.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The inherently subjective nature of assessing the Critical View of Safety (CVS), depending on clinical expertise and exposure to laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos, accurately reflects real-world scenarios in the operating room. This variable was captured in the annotation difficulty rating provided by each annotator for each case and serves as the foundation for the uncertainty-centered sub-challenge. To ensure standardized, consistent, and reproducible assessment of the CVS criteria among all annotators a detailed annotation protocol was provided, including visual examples in the form of flashcards and reference annotations based on the interrater agreement of three annotators per datapoint were provided.

To address the common error source of annotator fatigue and ensure a clear understanding and continuous implementation of the CVS annotation protocol, the SAGES CVS Challenge organizers implemented regular communication with annotators including email feedback and virtual calls. Given that the annotation period spans several months, annotator fatigue was mitigated by distributing small batches for annotation in regular time intervals.

Errors in segmentation annotation can be classified into three categories: (1) missed object/structure (false negative), (2) incorrectly annotated object/structure (false positive), and (3) boundary errors, cases where the segmentation boundaries of a structure are inaccurate. We focus particularly on mitigating the first two types of errors, specifically instructing annotation reviewers to flag every instance of such errors. By following multiple rounds of annotation review, we also minimize the likelihood of such errors.

Meanwhile, for the boundary errors, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.10916> delineates a list of cases with guidelines on how to specifically segment the boundaries. Indeed, there are cases that exist beyond the realms of this guideline, in which case we consider the ground-truth to represent multiple plausible but naturally variant scenarios.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Other potential error sources include variability in the dataset due to rare combinations of underlying factors and labels, as well as imperfect estimates of underlying distributions uncertainty and robustness. These will be monitored through the resampling of the datasets.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Subchallenges A, B - CVS Classification

Primary metric:

Mean Average Precision (mAP) and Mean Squared Error (MSE/Brier Score)

Secondary Metrics:

Per-class Counting Metric: Positive Likelihood Ratio (LR+)

Multi-class Counting Metric: Balanced Accuracy (BA)

Robustness measure: The same base metric as the primary one (mAP) will be used, but checked over a set of distribution-shifted modified validation set. The overall metric will use a norm that is close to L norm in order to check distributional robustness. The 90% quantile will be used to reduce outlier effects, and yet keep the maximum norm behavior needed for robustness reasoning.

Subchallenge C - Hepatocystic Anatomy Segmentation

Primary Metric: mAP@50, shifting the focus to correctly identifying all relevant structures and sufficiently localizing them

Secondary Metrics:

mAP@75, mAP@25, allowing us to measure both how much of a bottleneck accurate localization is, and how different approaches vary in localization capability.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Subchallenges A and B

In the 2024 challenge, there were 3 sub-challenges that evaluated A SINGLE per-frame CVS classification model in different scenarios, aiming to test different aspects of model performance. Namely:

Overall CVS Classification: Performance on per-frame CVS criteria prediction, where the ground truth is generated by majority vote consensus of 3 annotators. Performance is measured as the mean average precision (mAP) across all annotated frames and each criterion.

Uncertainty-Aware CVS Classification: Performance on per-frame CVS criteria prediction, but the ground-truth is recomputed to take into account annotation confidence. As the resulting ground-truth is probabilistic, performance is measured using mean squared error (lower is better), averaged across frames then across criteria. The confidence-aware ground-truth is computed as follows:

CVS Classification Robustness: Performance on per-frame CVS criteria prediction, but the testing videos are divided into numerous subsets representing potential data distribution shifts when moving to "unseen" data. A subset mAP is computed for each of these subsets, then all the subset mAP values are averaged to obtain the Robustness mAP.

In clinical practice, solutions should jointly optimize for each of these scenarios. As a result, for the 2025 challenge, we will rank each submission based on each of these 3 metrics, then average the 3 ranks to obtain the final rank. Ties will be broken based on overall CVS classification rank.

Justification for mAP: CVS classification is a complex task for various reasons: (1) the CVS is a video-based concept that has been formalized into an image-based classification task for modeling purposes, CVS assessment can be subjective, particularly during dissection, there is inherent data-based uncertainty (motion blur, uncertainty surrounding anatomy identification), and the label distribution is highly imbalanced. As a result, we opt for a multi-threshold metric (mAP) as one of our primary metrics as opposed to single-threshold metrics like accuracy or F1 score. Doing so enables analyzing potential performance for different clinical applications of these models, where different thresholds could be used (e.g. for reporting vs. for guidance). For the uncertainty-awareness evaluation, however, mAP cannot be evaluated because the reference labels are continuous values between 0 and 1, by formulation. Moreover, the objective of the uncertainty-awareness evaluation is to test whether model

confidence outputs are aligned with human annotator confidence. Using mean-squared error enables testing the latter, making it a well-suited evaluation metric.

Running the same metrics over different computational tiers will allow us to isolate the effect of limited inference compute on CVS classification performance. As mentioned earlier, ensuring that the evaluations run in a reasonable time-frame (6 frames per second), can plausibly enable different downstream applications (real-time as well as post-hoc).

Subchallenge C

Because each disjoint segment of each anatomical structure is annotated as a separate instance, we treat the anatomical segmentation task as a vanilla instance segmentation task, and therefore apply canonical instance segmentation metrics to evaluate performance.

We will use COCO Segmentation mAP@0.5 as the primary evaluation metric(see <https://cocodataset.org/#detection-eval>). By fixing the IoU threshold at 0.5 instead of considering a range from [0.5, 0.95] (traditional COCO Segmentation mAP), we can evaluate how well models capture the surgical scene without overly penalizing boundary errors (e.g. boundary between gallbladder and cystic duct, extent of cystic plate, etc.). Meanwhile, secondary evaluations will capture how the mAP is affected by lower and higher IoU thresholds.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

For subchallenges A and B, we calculate all the metrics at a video (case) level and then average across all considered cases. Ranking will be according to the average score.

For subchallenge C, we calculate the metrics at the dataset level, because each video has only 3 annotated frames, making robust evaluation at the video level difficult.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Incomplete submissions or submissions missing results will be disqualified.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

We calculate all the metrics at a video (case) level and then average across all considered cases. Ranking will be according to the average score.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or

- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will use paired significance tests to explore the statistical significance of the boosts between different submissions. We will also explore the variance in performance of the submitted methods overall on a per-video level. All benchmarking will be performed using Python.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Standard approach for benchmarking validation, with some testing of robustness due to domain shifts as sampled across variations in main factors for which we presume there's enough data to characterize distributions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will explore common failure modes, and common methodological characteristics of successful and unsuccessful submissions, and generate qualitative videos on test cases representing underrepresented characteristics.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A